

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA'LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

BUXORO DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI

**EFFECTIVE WAYS OF ORGANIZING
LEARNER CENTERED CLASSES
IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOM**

Xalqaro miqyosdagi ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI TO'PLAMI

23 APREL , 2024

« Effective ways of organizing Learner Centered Classes in English language classroom» xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari.

Buxoro – 2024 - 359-bet

Buxoro davlat universiteti rektori O.X.Xamidovning 2024 yil 9 mart 146-U-sonli buyrug‘i asosida 2024 yil 23-aprel kuni “Effective ways of organizing Learner Centered Classes in English language classroom” mavzusidagi xalqaro miqyosdagi ilmiy-amaliy anjumani bo‘lib o‘tadi.

Mas'ul muharrir:

Mirzaev Ibodullo Kamolovich – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor

Tahrir hay'ati:

N.B. Ataboyev, D.I. Xodjaeva, F.M.Xajieva, G.P. Nazarova,
M.B.Axmedova, O.X.Ganieva, A.A. Fayzieva, S.B. Xamdamova,
G.I. Xamraeva, N.S. Zokirova, L.X.Xaydarova,

Taqrizchilar:

Rasulov Zubaydullo Izomovich – filologiya fanlari doktori, dosent
Qosimova Nafisa Farxodovna - filologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori,
dosent

Maqolalarni to'plovchi va nashrga tayyorlovchi Ingliz adabiyotshunosligi va tarjimashunoslik kafedrasida o'qituvchilari L.X.Xaydarova va N.S. Zokirova

Ushbu to'plamda jamlangan maqolalar qiyosiy tilshunoslik, tarjimashunoslik va madaniyatlararo muloqot masalalari, qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik va adabiy oqimlar rivoji masalalari, xorijiy tillarni o'qitishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari va istiqbollari, O'zbekistonda tarjima maktabi yaratish va uni rivojlantirishda innovatsion g'oya va texnologiyalarni qo'llash masalalari doirasida mutaxassislarning tajriba va fikr almashinuvini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi.

References:

1. Yoldoshev B. Fundamentals of phraseological methodology: Textbook - Samarkand, 1999. B-206.
2. Uzbek folk proverbs. T. Mirzaev. - Tashkent, 2005.
3. Malcolm Mann. Direction C1, C2 Grammar and Vocabulary – Macmillan. 201
4. Rakhmatullaev Sh. Explanatory phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1978. B 407.
5. www.phrases.com

THE NOTION OF LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY IN TRANSLATION STUDIES

Ruzieva Mahfuza Khikmatovna

Bukhara State University, English literature and translation studies department

Abstract: *The given article below discusses different viewpoints on anthropocentric paradigm – Linguistic personality which is one of the modern terms in translation studies.*

Key words: *Linguistic personality, translator’s personality, anthropocentric paradigm, human mental activity, communicative behavior, culture and society.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются различные точки зрения на антропоцентрическую парадигму – языковую личность, которая является одним из современных терминов в переводоведении.*

Ключевые слова: *языковая личность, личность переводчика, антропоцентрическая парадигма, психическая деятельность человека, коммуникативное поведение, культура и общество.*

At the end of the 20th century language and the following anthropocentric paradigm – “linguistic personality” was studied from the perspective of native speakers. Issues related to the feelings of a person forced to live within the

constraints of a particular language were investigated, and the processes of human mental activity reflected in language were analyzed. The concept of a linguistic personality has become increasingly popular. The reality around a person is transformed through thinking into a system of images that form a picture of the world. The anthropocentric nature of the worldview is expressed in its focus on humans. According to V.N. Teliya, the anthropocentric canon, a “naive picture of the world” is created that finds expression in the very possibility of thinking about natural phenomena or abstract concepts as objectified constants. The linguistic picture of the world is based on the anthropocentric principle, which states that man is the measure of all things”. It should be noted that the ideas that led to the concept of the “linguistic picture of the world” in the late 20th century were present long before their formulation. V. von Humboldt, one of the first linguists and philosophers, suggested that language reflects the worldview of its speakers: “different languages are the organs of the original thinking and perception of nations”.

These ideas were further developed by Leo Weisgerber in his research. He introduced the concept of a linguistic picture to the scientific terminology. The linguistic picture of the world is, on the one hand, a result of the historical development of an ethnos and its language, and on the other hand, it shapes the path of its further development. The linguistic picture can be seen as a living organism with a complex structure that includes multiple levels. Linguistic expression is a special set of sounds, sound combinations, and features of the articulatory apparatus in native speakers. It includes prosodic characteristics, vocabulary, word formation capabilities, syntax, and phrase and sentence structure. Additionally, it includes the paremiological baggage of the language.

The linguistic picture of the world shapes the overall communicative behavior, understanding of nature and man's inner world, and the language system. Thinking and the native language are used to perceive the world. L. Weisgerber believed that the way we reflect reality is idiosyncratic and

corresponds to the static form of the language. To what extent a person speaks the language determines how well they know the world. The world is also discussed in the works of American linguists, Edward Sapir and Benjamin Whorf, who created the unique theory of linguistic relativity. They argue that a person navigates the world without the help of language, and that language is just a tool to solve specific problems of communication and thinking. Sapir writes that the idea that language is an essential part of our perception of the world is an illusion. Indeed, he argues that the world is largely built on the linguistic habits and conventions of a particular social group. Moreover, V.A. Maslova believes that the linguistic picture of the world is a common cultural heritage of the nation, which is structured and multilevel. This linguistic picture of the world determines communicative behavior and understanding of the external and internal world of a person, reflecting the way of speech-thinking activity that is characteristic of a particular era with its spiritual, cultural, and national values.

Indeed, the words about human communicative behavior in this statement by V.A. Maslova are important, as the linguistic picture of the world largely determines communication in one society or another. The concept of linguistic personality in anthropological linguistics is extremely significant, as this concept is the tool that creates language varieties. If the question of how language is created is still unanswered, this is understandable. Based on the presence of numerous theories and hypotheses about the origin of language, it can be concluded that language varieties, including social and territorial variants, are created by people.

In other words, linguistic personalities play a significant role in the formation of language. A linguistic personality can be defined as a person, who is an integral part of the world. The issue of the manifestation of the primary world in the secondary world is fundamental and essential for human existence. The concept of "linguistic personality" began to take shape in Russian linguistics in the 1930s, with the first mention in the work by V.V. Vinogradov, "On Fiction".

Analyzing the state of affairs regarding the literary language in the period of 1929-1930, Vinogradov noted that I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay eliminated the methods of historical analysis and historicism from his studies of literary language. He was interested in the linguistic personality as a receptacle for socio-linguistic forms and norms, as well as the focus of mixing and crossing of different socio-linguistic categories.

The creation of the theory of linguistic personality, which has been widely accepted since the late 1980s, belongs to Y.N. Karaulov. The scientific school "Russian Language Personality" defines two phenomena by language personality: a specific native speaker of a particular language and culture, characterized on the basis of analysis of texts produced by them, from the perspective of the specific use of systemic structural means of that language to reflect their vision and assessment of surrounding reality (worldview), and to achieve communicative goals. In this world, there are certain goals and a comprehensive way to describe an individual's linguistic ability. This involves a systematic representation of language and its functioning in the processes of generating texts. Y.N. Karaulov emphasizes that the linguistic personality is a cross-cutting idea that permeates all aspects of language learning and destroys the boundaries between disciplines studying a person. It is impossible to study a person outside his language.

Recently, the linguistic personality has been studied from the perspective of its varieties related to human activity. A professional linguistic personality stands out, which defines a professional as a set of intellectual, socio-cultural, and moral-volitional qualities formed in a special professional and cultural environment. These qualities are reflected in the properties of a person's language. The study of linguistic personality involves the analysis of consciousness, behavior and activity. It is revealed in the peculiarities of linguistic and speech units produced by the individual, as well as in the originality of their professional discourse, which is subordinated to the goals and objectives of professional activity. There are different types of linguistic personalities,

including a professionally oriented one, an unprofessional one, and a linguistically undirected one. A professional linguistic personality can experience the influence of national cognitive thinking characteristic of the language they use.

In conclusion, the study of linguistic personality continues to be an important area of research. Linguistic personality is considered an independent phenomenon that deserves further investigation. The types of linguistic personalities are analyzed and the reasons influencing their formation are investigated. A linguistic personality is a complex concept that is influenced by various factors. One of the main reasons for this is that each person has a unique cognitive space, which is a structured set of knowledge and ideas. This individual cognitive space plays an important role in shaping a person's linguistic personality. human thinking plays a role. The creative understanding of the surrounding world by a linguistic personality is creatively reflected in the language by the appearance of new linguistic lexical and grammatical forms. Each linguistic personality has its own individual thinking, which becomes a component of social thinking, and social thinking, in turn, becomes a component of national thinking.

List of used literature:

1. Telia V.N., Doroshenko A.V. Linguoculturology is the key to the new reality of the phenomenon of reproducibility of multiple–word formations // Language. Culture. Communication: A collection of scientific papers in honor of the anniversary of S.G.Ter-Minasova. – M.: Gnosis, 2008.
2. Humboldt V. von, Selected works on linguistics. – M.: Progress, 1984. – 397 p.
3. Weisgerber J.L. Native language and the formation of the spirit. // Translated from German, introductory article and commentary by O. A. Radchenko. – M.1993. – 232 p.
4. Sepir E. Selected works on linguistics and cultural studies. – M.: Progress, 1993. – 656 p.

5. Maslova V.A. Introduction to cognitive linguistics.- 3rd edition, reprint. – M.: Flint: Nauka, 2007. 294 p.

GENDER AND LANGUAGE USE

Kaxorova Nargiza Nusratovna

Buxoro davlat universiteti “ Ingliz adabiyotshunosligi va
tarjimashunoslik” kafedrasi assistenti
kaxorovanargiza5@gmail.com

Abstract: This research paper analyses the aspects of language, gender, ethnicity in terms of sociolinguistic perspective. Specifically, it focuses on researches carried out on the usage of language structures and written language by explaining broader trajectories in language practice. The paper provides nuanced and contextualised explanations about several historical approaches adopted by many scholars with valuable contributions to interpret the sociolinguistic study of language and how it works. It gives a wide range of information about linguistic features and sophisticated sociolinguistic patternings based on variationist approaches regarding gender, ethnic and other distinctions in learning the language as well as impartialities in language use.

Key words: Sociolinguistic, trajectories, patternings, variationist, gender, distinctions, impartialities. ,

Аннотация: В данной исследовательской работе анализируются аспекты языка, пола и этнической принадлежности с точки зрения социолингвистической перспективы. В частности, он фокусируется на исследованиях использования языковых структур и письменной речи путем объяснения более широких траекторий языковой практики. В статье представлены детальные и контекстуализированные объяснения нескольких исторических подходов, принятых многими учеными, которые внесли